

ICT-BASED NEEDS ANALYSIS OF LEARNING ARTS AND CULTURE IN MIDDLE SCHOOL AT SUNGGAL

Qothrun Nada Ma'ruf Batubara

Faculty of Engineering, Universitas Negeri Padang, Padang, Sumatra Barat, Indonesia

* Corresponding Author. E-mail: qothrunnadamb@gmail.com

Abstract

The use of ICT has begun to be developed and implemented at almost all levels of education, from elementary, junior high school/middle school to senior high school education. Precisely at Sunggal 1 Public Middle School (SMP Negeri 1 Sunggal) is one of the schools that maximizes the use of ICT. The needs assessment was implemented with the aimed of improving the planning of further educational programs related to the learning process, starting from planning, development, utilization, and management to assessment. The data collection technique used in this research was by distributing questionnaires to students and teachers, followed by conducting classroom observations. This research used a Likert scale calculation method and qualitative descriptive. Teachers predominantly use lecture and discussion methods during the learning process. Assisted by projector technology and PowerPoint slide media, offline learning is more fun.

Keywords: ICT, arts and culture, learning needs

INTRODUCTION

Learning activities must undergo a change from offline (face-to-face) to online (digital). Regarding this, technology plays a major role in it. The use of technology in society is greatly increasing. Almost all fields of activity in the world have begun to maximize the use of technology, including the field of education. Education is a field that has been utilized in its implementation, including in the implementation of the learning process (Suyanto, 2001).

Sunggal 1 Public Middle School is one of the schools that really pays attention to the use of technology. One of them is ICT-based learning. The role of the teacher is very important in learning activities because it can influence students' knowledge, attitudes and skills. Competent teachers have a huge opportunity to produce competent students too. This is in line with developments in

science and technology in the implementation of learning.

A learning process that is oriented towards student-based learning or learning that makes students actors who dominate activities, have the opportunity to achieve the goals of education (Fisal, 2011). Educational technology is an asset and a process that can be utilized optimally as a medium that can help the learning process.

As an asset, technology is certainly easier to use because it is more effective and efficient in many things, for example, the use of projector technology, and so on (Miarso, 1987). As a process, educational technology is also abstract because it involves procedures, ideas, and human resources to analyze problems and find solutions while managing these solutions as something that can fulfill the goals of education.

The era of globalization is a challenge for the education sector to be able to prepare

Submitted	Accepted	Published
09-10-2023	04-12-2023	04-12-2023

reliable human resources in the field of science and technology so they can compete in the global world. Technology can be utilized optimally, knowledge is needed that can support this so that it can answer the challenges of competition in the global world (Oktarina, 2007).

Until now, ICT has developed very rapidly in the world of education (Al-Ansi et al., 2021). Its use is also evenly distributed at almost all levels of education. Sunggal 1 Public Middle School is quite good at using ICT. Needs analysis is a very important process to pay attention to. Starting from lesson planning to supervision of learning. Everything must be analyzed thoroughly according to the goals of education. This research aimed to identify the factors needed by teachers and students of Sunggal 1 Middle School for ICT-based learning activities.

The learning process can occur because of the interaction between teachers and students. Learning is a process carried out between individuals with the aim of achieving overall changes in behavior as a result of the individual's own experience in interacting with their environment (Surya, 2004). Learning is an activity that is carried out throughout life and can be carried out anytime, anywhere in almost every condition.

The learning process in class is only an activity that can further help direct understanding so that you can receive results that are directed and in line with expectations (Surya, 2004). Learning is an aspect of development that leads to change (modification) of behavior as a result of practice and experience (Hamalik, 2010). Having learning activities designed using a system to achieve certain goals, can help achieve educational goals optimally.

METHOD

Technology and learning can be stated as the best combination that can improve educational processes, goals, and objectives. Technology has become a medium that students can use to obtain new information and knowledge and use existing knowledge as a basis for taking action. Technology as a supporting tool for efforts to improve skills in implementing learning (Ramli, 2012).

Learning and teaching technology is theory and practice in the design, development, utilization, management, and evaluation of processes and resources for learning. Technology areas for learning and teaching, are as follows (Warsita, 2008). Includes principles and procedures for applying theory, and designing learning activities systematically, such as designing systems, messages, and strategies for studying certain hypotheses, but only by describing the conditions of the variables as they are.

The data collection process was carried out by distributing questionnaires to teachers and students of Sunggal 1 Middle School, as well as by conducting direct observations over a while. The data obtained is the result obtained from the data collection technique. Based on this definition, needs assessment can be carried out in four phases as follows: (1) what should be: ensuring what should be there by identifying and prioritizing the goals to be achieved; (2) what is: defines what exists by determining the conditions and goals that have a relationship; (3) discrepancy or the difference between the expectations to be achieved and the conditions occurring in the field and identifying needs; and (4) priorities: prioritizing needs starting from the most urgent, feasible, and feasible.

This research used a descriptive qualitative method. This method was chosen because the assessment process was not intended to examine a particular hypothesis, but only to describe the condition of the variables as they are (Arikunto, 2010). The data collection process was carried out by distributing questionnaires to Arts and Culture teachers and students of Sunggal 1 Middle School, as well as by conducting direct observations over a while. The data obtained was the result obtained from the data collection technique.

This research method includes determining the population and sample, research instruments, and data collection techniques, as well as data analysis techniques which are the methods or methods used to carry out research.

The population in this research was Arts and Culture teachers and students at Sunggal 1 Public Middle School. The population in this research was 35 people. The sampling method in this research was purposive random sampling. Sampling in this way was a random sampling technique with certain considerations. Data calculation from the questionnaire carried out was a Likert scale calculation with a description of the calculation table as in Table 1 below.

Table 1. Calculation Description

Code	Respondent Type	Response Value
SS	Strongly agree	Value = 10
S	Agree	Value = 8
N	Neutral	Value = 6
TS	Don't agree	Value = 4
STS	Strongly Disagree	Value = 2
Y= Number of Respondents X Largest Response Value		
X= Number of Respondents X Smallest Response Value		

The method used in collecting data in this research was to use primary data sources, namely research data sources obtained directly from the source. In this case, the primary data was in the form of the results of a questionnaire by Arts and Culture teachers and students at Sunggal 1 Public Middle School.

The data collection technique used a survey method by distributing questionnaires to respondents, namely Arts and Culture teachers, and students at Sunggal 1 Public Middle School. Researchers distributed questionnaires by visiting potential respondents one by one. The distribution was carried out in the junior high school environment.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Description and Calculation of Observation Results and Distribution of Questionnaires to Students and Teachers using Likert scale calculations

From the results of observations and data calculations based on distributing questionnaires to students and teachers regarding questions regarding the process of implementing learning carried out at Sunggal

1 Public Middle School, data obtained was 62.3% more in favor of offline (face-to-face) learning by maximizing the use of ICT because makes the process of understanding learning material easier, especially for practical subjects.

Table 2. Results of Calculation of Questionnaire Data Using the Likert Scale Method

SS	10	Mark	10	Results	100
S	5	Mark	8	Results	40
N	7	Mark	6	Results	42
TS	5	Mark	4	Results	20
STS	8	Mark	2	Results	16
Amount	35			Total	218
Y	350				
X	70				
Index Percentage = Total/YX100 =				62.28571429	

Students and teachers admitted that they experienced several obstacles to the implementation of monotonous learning due to students' lack of understanding of the activities that would be carried out during practice. It will be easier for the teacher to monitor to ensure whether the student in question really understands or is just pretending to understand. Likewise for theoretical subjects. So rather than implementing learning activities, teachers should be expected to greatly increase the use of ICT.

The implementation of learning at Sunggal 1 Public Middle School has utilized ICT in almost all conditions, such as implementing online and offline learning. Even in these two conditions, it is still possible for teachers and students to continue implementing the discussion method or lecture method. This proves that the development of ICT utilization at Sunggal 1 Public Middle School is very adequate. Of course, this is because there is support from the school so that its implementation can have the same positive impact felt by students and teachers.

Based on data received from distributing questionnaires and observations in the field, management of ICT utilization can be realized because there is a coordinator

who is responsible for the completeness of equipment supporting ICT utilization. The management carried out by the school facilities and infrastructure section is to openly allow teachers to submit suggestions for learning needs that can support ICT-based learning activities.

Sunggal 1 Public Middle School has maximized the management of ICT utilization, such as by paying attention to the number and condition of projector technology, and by ensuring guidance for students and teachers involved in it. The evaluation of ICT-based learning was carried out by researchers by providing a statement form regarding the implementation of learning at the end of the semester.

This is the basis for the school to continue to make improvements and continue to strive for the best for all school members so that they can carry out adequate and enjoyable learning. Because more students feel that online learning is less effective, it is an evaluation material for each teaching staff to be able to increase the utilization of learning using ICT so that later the percentage index of students who approve of offline learning can be balanced with students who choose online learning using ICT itself.

CONCLUSION

The implementation of ICT-based learning has several factors that can support this use, including: ensuring teacher competency in the use of ICT by continuing to guide the teachers and students concerned; providing equipment needed for learning implementation that can maximize the use of ICT in learning activities, such as providing projector technology; management, planning, and supervision are still carried out to ensure that ICT utilization is maintained; the ability to solve problems more systematically in the implementation of the learning being held; and ability to develop and evaluate learning from each individual to support the use of ICT. Based on the results of the research that has been carried out, the things above can be supporting factors so that later online and offline learning can run in balance following the curriculum and educational objectives of the agency itself. Then also so that

the percentage of satisfaction and the choice of learning between offline and online can be balanced both in terms of satisfaction and the learning objectives of each meeting, both offline and online itself.

REFERENCES

- Al-Ansi, A. M., Garad, A., & Al-Ansi, A. (2021). ICT-Based Learning During Covid-19 Outbreak: Advantages, Opportunities and Challenges. *Gagasan Pendidikan Indonesia*, 2(1), 10-26.
- Arikunto, S. (2010). *Research Methods*. Jakarta: Rineka Cipta
- Fisal, M. (2011). *The Influence of the Effectiveness of Use and Trust in Information Systems Technology on the Performance of the National Community Empowerment Program (PNPM) Mandiri Urban Facilitators in Palembang City*. Thesis, Master of Management Postgraduate Program, Bina Danna University, Palembang.
- Hamalik, O. (2010). *Teaching and Learning Process*. Bandung: Earth of Letters.
- Suyanto. (2001). *Reflections and Educational Reform in Indonesia Entering the Third Millennium*. Yogyakarta: Adicita.
- Miarso, Y. (1987). *Philosophical and Theoretical Foundations of Educational Technology*. Jakarta: UNJ Postgraduate Faculty.
- Oktarina, N. (2007). The Role of Global Education in Improving the Quality of Human Resources. *Unnes Educational Dynamics*, 2(3), 61996
- Ramli, M. (2012). *Learning Media and Technology*. Banjarmasin: Antasari Press.
- Surya, M. (2004). *Psychology of Learning and Teaching*. Bandung: PustakaBani Quraish.
- Warsita, B. (2008). *Basic Learning Technology and Its Applications*. Jakarta: Rineka Cipta.